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D5.2 Plan for dissemination, communication and exploitation

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31.07.24

Project title: Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition

Project acronym: RE4GREEN

Grant Agreement no.: 101131706

Lead contractor for this deliverable: NTUA

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Deliverable factsheet:

Action:	101131706, RE4GREEN, Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition
Lead author(s):	Nicole Sarla and Panagiotis Kavouras
Dissemination level:	PU – Public
Document type:	Report
Work Package:	5
Due date according to contract:	31 July 2024
Contributor(s):	NTUA
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Keywords:	Dissemination, communication, exploitation

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7.	Partner	National Technical University of Athens	NTUA	Greece
8.	Partner	European Association of Research Managers & Administrators	EARMA	European network
9.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	European network
10.	Partner	Korean University	KU	Korea
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13.	Partner	Amsterdam UMC	VUMC	Netherlands
14.	Partner	Women Engage for a Common Future	WECF	International Network
15.	Partner	University of Tokyo	UTokyo	Japan

Revision History

Version	Date	Revised by	Reason
0.1	30.05.24	Nicole Sarla	Preparation of the 1st draft
0.2	25.06.24	Panagiotis Kavouras	Comments to the 1st draft; preparation of the 2nd draft
0.3	27.06.24	Nicole Sarla	Preparation of the 2nd draft
0.4	02.07.24	Carly Seedall	Review
0.5	16.07.24	Alexandra Csabi	Review
0.6	16.07.24	Michael Bernstein	Review
0.7	23.07.24	Nicole Sarla	Edit and apply recommendations from review
0.8	29.07.24	Panagiotis Kavouras	Final editing
1.0	29.07.24	Nicole Sarla	Final version

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List of abbreviations

ALLEA	All European Academies
CEI	Central European Initiative
CSO	Civil society organisation
DEC	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication
DoA	Description of Action
ENERI	European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity
ENRIO	European Network of Research Integrity Offices
ERA	European Research Area
EUA	European University Association
EURODOC	European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers
GYA	Global Youth Academy
KER	Key exploitable results
KPI	Key performance indicator
LERU	League of European Research Universities
NCP	National contact point
ORE	Open Research Europe
PV	Promotional video
RI	Research integrity
RIO	Research integrity officer
RPM	Research policymaker
RPO	Research-performing organisation
R&I	Research and innovation
RTO	Research/technology performing organization
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SME	Small–medium enterprise
STOA	Science and Technology Options Assessment
WP	Work package
YERUN	Young European Research Universities Network

Executive summary

RE4GREEN is dedicated to **advancing the Green Transition by developing a comprehensive ethics and integrity framework for research and innovation (R&I) that accounts for climate and environmental ethics.** To achieve this goal, RE4GREEN will collaborate with a multidisciplinary group of stakeholders, including representatives from academia, civil society, policy, and industry. **These goals highlight the importance for RE4GREEN to develop and implement a robust and ambitious plan for the dissemination, exploitation, and communication of the project's outputs.**

This report **outlines the stakeholder analysis and mapping exercise,** aiming to augment an initial version of the RE4GREEN Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan found in the Grant Agreement and facilitate the engagement of stakeholders.

Introduction

RE4GREEN project summary

Environmental and climate-related challenges are global and reach all sectors of society. However, research and innovation (R&I) activities that address these challenges may carry substantial unintended implications. RE4GREEN aims to contribute to a European Research Area ethics and integrity framework for R&I activities designed to reduce the risk from such implications and to support the transition to a sustainable economy and society as envisioned by the European Green Deal. RE4GREEN will reflect diverse stakeholder views and relate them to cross-cutting environmental and climate-related ethics issues by applying a bottom-up social lab methodology. RE4GREEN's framework will consist of operational research ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and training materials for researchers, ethics and integrity experts and advisors, and ethics reviewers to ensure R&I activities support the Green Transition.

Objectives

RE4GREEN seeks to bring together a diverse and multidisciplinary group of researchers, members of ethics committees and integrity bodies, civil society organisations, policymakers, and industry representatives to shape a holistic ethics and integrity framework for R&I that supports the Green Transition. To address its objectives, RE4GREEN will bring together a diverse, multidisciplinary group of stakeholders, including researchers, members of ethics committees and integrity bodies, international partners, and stakeholder advisory board (SAB) members, and leverage the multiplying force of key networks connected to its consortium. The project will aim to strengthen foundational research; enable bottom-up approaches; enhance the relevance of training materials; facilitate long-term, post-project outcomes; and ensure the sustainability of outputs. **Given the ambitious nature of these core objectives, the RE4GREEN project requires a robust and ambitious plan to amplify the project's impact and to ensure the sustainability of outputs.**

This deliverable presents an augmented DEC plan, building on a draft included in the proposal. This draft outlined different types of dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities, defined as follows:

1. **Dissemination activities:** sharing the project's outputs with relevant stakeholders and potential users to maximise its impact in the public domain.

2. **Exploitation activities:** streamlining the project's core outputs to key stakeholders for specific applications, thereby enhancing the practical application of the RE4GREEN results.
3. **Communication activities:** promoting the project in its totality (i.e., its progress, results, and outputs as well as the societal challenges it addresses) in accordance with its branding, thereby reaching a broader audience, spreading awareness, and enhancing the project's visibility to the media and the public.

The DEC plan, drafted and monitored within work package 5 (WP5), details how RE4GREEN will raise awareness of the project's findings and outputs, promote the uptake of these findings and outputs, and boost the exploitation and sustainability of its outcomes. Simultaneously, DEC activities are a collective responsibility of all RE4GREEN consortium members.

The project's dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) work package, WP5, led by NTUA, will enhance the visibility of RE4GREEN's progress and outputs throughout the project's duration. In this capacity, WP5 will act as a bridge between RE4GREEN and relevant stakeholders to boost the uptake of project results. Given the cardinal role of dissemination and communication in raising project awareness, DEC activities must be supported by a strong and inclusive brand identity (introduced in D5.1) and a robust DEC.

This deliverable is a report on the stakeholder analysis and mapping exercise; it aims to augment an initial version of the RE4GREEN Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan and facilitate the engagement of stakeholders (under Task 5.1: Augment the Plan for Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation).

Maximising impact

The RE4GREEN project will focus on three key activities to maximise its impact throughout the duration and after the completion of the project:

- i. Wide dissemination and communication of RE4GREEN progress, events, results, outputs, and outcomes.
- ii. Active involvement of all relevant RE4GREEN stakeholders and future users in the development and implementation of the project's outputs.
- iii. Commitment to open science practices, including open-access scientific publications (as described in detail in D6.2: Data Management Plan; see Eghbali & Fisher, 2024). RE4GREEN's dedication to open science entails making the project's results and outputs openly accessible. This supports the maximisation of the project's impact through its widespread diffusion to the public and the scientific community.

DEC activities are led by NTUA and are accompanied by defined objectives, enabling the consortium's collective effort to engage stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement throughout the project will increase awareness of the research ethics and research integrity needs in relation to the Green Transition and highlight RE4GREEN's activities to address these needs. These activities include the Social Labs (WP2); consultation on guidelines, risk assessment, and policy recommendations (WP2 and WP3); training (WP4); and project-wide dissemination activities (WP5). Stakeholder engagement will be further strengthened through the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB; including representatives from the European Network of Research Integrity Offices – ENRIO, European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers – EURODOC, and All European Academies – ALLEA – networks) and the inclusion of several key stakeholder networks (including EUREC, EARMA, European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity – ENERI, ECSA, and the Embassy of Good

Science), which will provide sustainable opportunities for uptake of the project's outputs after the end of the project. International partners will anchor efforts to maximise impact in their respective regions.

During the kick-off meeting, a WP5-led workshop introduced RE4GREEN's communication, dissemination, and exploitation approach, including the project branding. Consortium partners were encouraged to create and share input for the work package and to use their networks to multiply project messages; additionally, it was established that the project should consider communication norms in other cultures and contexts. During the workshop, two boards were hung in the meeting room and were filled out by consortium members. These boards collected partners' ideas concerning possible collaboration with other projects; third-party or consortium network events; possible social media connections; recommendations for material to be included in the newsletter; relevant academic journals and possible manuscript topics; relevant science e-magazines and/or blogs; topics to include in the promotional videos; and relevant conferences (see Annex).

Target groups, stakeholders, and scale

Defining target groups is crucial because it ensures that efforts and resources are directed towards those most likely to be interested in and benefit from the project's results. By focusing on specific groups, the project can achieve greater impact and efficiency to meet the precise needs of its audience, thereby improving successful project implementation.

The operational ethics and integrity guidelines and training materials and programmes developed by RE4GREEN will be shared with a minimum of 1000 students and researchers at early, middle, and senior stages (WP4); 400 research managers, 100 citizen scientists, 800 research ethics and integrity experts (including a minimum of 400 Horizon Europe ethics appraisal scheme experts); and a minimum of 90 participants in the Social Labs based in Europe (WP2) as well as 30 internationally, connected to Pillar II Clusters and key Green Transition-related Missions in Horizon Europe. In addition, consortium partners will use RE4GREEN insights and outputs to advance change within their own organisations (project partners will promote uptake of RE4GREEN findings and resources, for example through internal webinars or integration into existing organisational research ethics and integrity materials and courses). The project will directly engage a minimum of 15 policymakers at the EU level during the development of the project's policy recommendations (WP3). These recommendations will be disseminated to a minimum of 100 policymakers, primarily at the EU level.

The stakeholders of the RE4GREEN's results and outputs are as follows:

1. Research ethics committee (REC) members
2. Research integrity experts
3. Researchers and research-performing organisations (RPOs)
4. Industry (including small–medium enterprises – SMEs)
5. Research managers
6. Policymakers
7. Research funders
8. Students, graduates, and postdocs in universities
9. National contact points (NCPs) of consortium member countries

Other relevant stakeholders include the following:

10. Civil society organisations
11. Citizen scientists and the general public
12. Publishers and editors

Different stakeholder groups will be targeted by RE4GREEN outputs, interconnected with the project's core objectives. Table 1 presents an overview of the target groups, outcomes, and impacts. The project's impacts and exploitation activities are thoroughly analysed in the next section.

Target groups	Outcomes	Impacts
<p>Researchers at all career stages, with special attention to gender equality and participation;</p> <p>Research funders, civil society/ and general public, industry (incl. SMEs), policymakers, publishers, and citizen scientists who are stakeholders of Horizon Europe Clusters and Missions related to climate and environmental ethics and technologies;</p> <p>Research-performing organisations from countries across the spectrum of R&I performance;</p> <p>National and EU policymakers,</p> <p>Research ethics committee members, including Horizon Europe ethics appraisal experts, and research integrity experts;</p> <p>Research managers and administrators;</p> <p>National contact points.</p>	<p>Identification of key concepts and dimensions related to environment and climate ethics and integrity, also accounting for gaps in guidance and training sessions.</p> <p>More integrated ERA with cross-sector connections on climate and environmental ethics built through Social Lab relationships.</p> <p>Robust guidance and recommendations based on state-of-the-art integration of climate and environmental ethics with traditional research ethics and integrity resources.</p> <p>Novel climate and environmental ethics and integrity guidelines to support citizen scientists.</p> <p>Competence-based micromodules and training pathways taken up by students and researchers at all levels in research-performing organisations.</p> <p>Raised awareness and environmental and climate ethics competence of members of ethics review boards and Horizon Europe ethics appraisal experts.</p>	<p>Scientific impacts</p> <p>Enhanced integration of climate and environmental ethics issues into research ethics and integrity frameworks; enhanced understanding of climate and environmental ethics issues in R&I activities; more climate-neutral and environmentally sound R&I activities.</p> <p>Economic impacts</p> <p>Improved R&I system through integrating environment and climate ethics and integrity concerns in technology development for Green Transition; improved connections across ERA knowledge ecosystems; enhanced guidance on reducing harm and degradation of ecosystems, increasing equitable distribution of benefits and broadly accelerating R&I for Green Transition; enhanced environmental risk assessments to reduce incidence and cost of remediation.</p> <p>Societal impacts</p> <p>Better alignment of R&I with societal needs and values (e.g., inclusive gender equality, respect for the environment and its value</p>

		<p>for future generations); increased engagement of citizen scientists in R&I for the Green Transition; researchers better able to support Green Transition by addressing the "do no significant harm principle", environmental justice and other issues; better education and training of researchers for the Green Transition.</p>
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Table 1 – RE4GREEN target groups and key elements of the impact section

Plan for dissemination activities

Objectives

RE4GREEN's dissemination activities will target a wide and diverse array of stakeholders, who are considered instrumental in achieving impact. RE4GREEN's consortium members represent established networks that will catalyse the interaction with these stakeholders during the project's lifetime. An overview of the targeted stakeholders and the specific channels and tools for dissemination are presented in Table 2. In addition to the list presented in Table 2, the Social Labs will further support dissemination by connecting RE4GREEN with lab participants' networks and providing a minimum of 20 briefings at their various organisations.

As is depicted in the Table below (Table 2), RE4GREEN should engage these stakeholders in a variety of ways:

- i. through a series of co-creation events, such as Social Labs and training workshops and webinars
- ii. through oral and poster presentations at conferences
- iii. through the newsfeed of the RE4GREEN website
- iv. via the project's Social Media channels (LinkedIn and X – formerly known as Twitter)
- v. through the RE4GREEN outputs, communicated via project deliverables and publications.

Channels of dissemination

The engagement of relevant stakeholders will build upon the collaboration established since the beginning of the RE4GREEN project. An overview of the target stakeholders, the main channels of dissemination, and the specific channels and tools for dissemination are presented in Table 2.

Targeted stakeholders	Main channels of dissemination	Tools of dissemination
All types of stakeholders	Social Labs	16 virtual workshops and 16 in-person workshops
	RE4GREEN pilot training events and training sessions	Pilot training sessions: workshops with a physical presence (Task 4.2); training sessions: Embassy of Good Science, European Citizen Science, CORDIS, Zenodo platforms, RE4GREEN website
	Webinars	General and targeted webinars for organisations (internally & externally)
Research ethics committee members, research Integrity experts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Networks of RECs (e.g., EUREC, ENERI) o Networks of RIOs (e.g., members of ENRIO, ERION, ENERI) 	Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
	RE4GREEN website	Newsfeed
	RE4GREEN social media	Tweets, re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
	RE4GREEN website, academic journals, Zenodo	Deliverables, peer-reviewed publications

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Networks of experts (World Conferences on Research Integrity Foundation, ENAI, ENERI) 		
<p>Researchers, research-performing organisations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o In academia (faculty members, EARMA, the Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities, ALLEA) o Publicly & private universities and Research institutes (League of European Research Universities – LERU, European University Association – EUA, Young European Research Universities Network – YERUN, Global Youth Academy – GYA) <p>In industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Business Europe, Digital Europe, Eurochambres o SMEs (TRI) <p>Research managers (EARMA)</p>	<p>Conferences</p> <p>RE4GREEN website, journals, Zenodo</p> <p>RE4GREEN social media</p>	<p>Oral and poster presentations, bilateral meetings</p> <p>Deliverables, peer-reviewed publications</p> <p>Tweets, re-tweets, LinkedIn posts</p>
<p>Policymakers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o European Parliament o Members of European Parliament's Science and Technology Options Assessment (STOA) panel o EC officials o Members of Central European Initiative (CEI) 	<p>Engagement with policymakers</p> <p>Conferences</p> <p>RE4GREEN website</p> <p>RE4GREEN social media</p>	<p>Consultation meetings, policy briefs, written consultation & feedback</p> <p>Oral and poster presentations</p> <p>Newsfeed</p> <p>Tweets, re-tweets, LinkedIn posts</p>
<p>Research funders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o European Commission (especially the Ethics and Research Integrity Section) o Research funding associations (Humanities in the European Research Area, Ensuring Value in 	<p>Engagement with research funders</p> <p>Conferences</p> <p>RE4GREEN website</p> <p>RE4GREEN social media</p>	<p>Consultation meetings, policy briefs, written consultation & feedback</p> <p>Oral and poster presentations</p> <p>Newsfeed</p> <p>Tweets, re-tweets, LinkedIn posts</p>

Research, Science Europe, Wellcome Trust)		
Students, graduates, and postdocs at universities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EURODOC ○ Doctorate Plus of UBO ○ Global Research Ethics Programme of UN University 	Seminars and workshops	Webinars and/or on-site events (with emphasis on webinars that facilitate asynchronous attendance)
NCPs of consortium member countries	Direct contact	In-person or online as appropriate
Civil society organisations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open science communities ○ CSOs (Sense About Science, European Network of National Civil Society Associations, Civil Society Europe, WECF) 	Conferences	Oral and poster presentations
	RE4GREEN website	Newsfeed
Citizen scientists and general public <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Citizen Science Associations (e.g., ECSA) ○ Laypersons 	RE4GREEN social media	Tweets, re-tweets, LinkedIn posts
	RE4GREEN website, EU citizen science Platform, ECSA newsletter	Homepage, newsfeed
	RE4GREEN and ECSA social media	Tweets, re-tweets, LinkedIn posts

Table 2 – RE4GREEN dissemination strategy to raise awareness and promote uptake of results and outputs

Plan for exploitation activities

Objectives

The main exploitation activities will build upon the core outputs of RE4GREEN (i.e., analysis of environmental and climate ethics issues, operational “how-to” ethics and integrity guidelines, recommendations, and traditional and online training programmes). Table 3 presents the expected key exploitable results (KERs) of RE4GREEN and the respective targeted groups and exploitation routes. The achievement of KER is a collective responsibility of the consortium. The alignment of RE4GREEN with the exploitation routes will be monitored by the coordinating partner (UBO) and WP5 leaders.

In close collaboration with the whole consortium, WP5 leaders will promote uptake and the sustainability of the project’s outputs by operationalising the paths to impact and exploitation. The pathways toward expected outcomes and sustainable impacts will be driven by the bottom-up, network-based approach taken in RE4GREEN (see Figure 1). Impact will also build on and be driven by the strong track record of consortium partners in successfully developing and implementing ethics and integrity guidelines and training programmes in other scientific and technological domains (e.g., SHERPA, SIENNA, TechEthos, iRECS, SOPs4RI, TRUST, ROSiE) and the inclusion of diverse stakeholders throughout the project in the Social Labs (WP2) and advisory board (ENRIO and EURODOC).

Figure 1 – RE4GREEN bottom-up and network-based approach to impacts

Sustainability will be fostered by raising the visibility of the project's outputs to relevant networks like the ENERI e-Community; initiatives like the Embassy of Good Science; platforms like the SOPs4RI Toolbox and ROSiE Knowledge Hub; and institutions like the NCPs. WP5 will coordinate and promote project exploitation activities, including the following:

- *Packaging of Social Lab learnings (Task 2.5)*. In the last phase of the Social Labs, experiences and lessons will be drawn from across the workshops and interviews (including vignettes, best practices, exemplary activities, etc.) and packaged for distribution on the Embassy of Good Science and with ENERI. Specific attention will be paid to intercultural and topical considerations.
- *Consultations on guidelines (Task 3.2)*, primarily aimed at members of RECs, researchers, research managers, ethics and integrity experts, and Horizon Europe ethics appraisal experts. Specific guidelines will be produced for citizen scientists and address how researchers should engage with these actors—informed by ECSA's 10 Principles of Citizen Science (ECSA, 2015).
- *Recommendations for risk assessment and policy (Task 3.3 and Task 3.4)*, involving the dissemination of the policy recommendations through engagement with relevant policymakers. This would include direct consultation meetings and/or written consultation processes and participation in public consultations if and when these arise, at the national and EU level.
- *The implementation and dissemination of training programmes (Task 4.3)*, including an examination of how they can be implemented, and making training materials accessible on the Embassy of Good Science, ENERI, and the European Citizen Science Platform.

Social Lab participant briefings (minimum 20) and training will be utilised as exploitation pathways to promote the uptake of project outputs. The Social Lab outputs and training materials will be distributed on the Embassy of Good Science and ENERI to sustain bottom-up engagement (Social Lab outputs) and on the Embassy of Good Science, ENERI, and the European Citizen Science platform, with clear pathways for the different target groups (training materials).

WP5 will establish opportunities for deeper collaboration that will increase the uptake and integration of the project's outputs in different organisations both internally and externally, such as with the adoption of operational guidelines by universities, RECs, SMEs, RTOs, and CSOs carrying out research. UBO, KU, TRI IE, AIT, UCT, AU, EARMA, and EUREC will promote the uptake of RE4GREEN's findings and resources in their organisations, such as by hosting targeted webinars.

Exploitation routes

Table 3 presents the exploitation routes, detailing the specific benefits for the respective targeted groups expected to be affected by RE4GREEN's Key Exploitable Results (KERs). More specifically, this details how RE4GREEN provides recommendations for supporting the transition to a sustainable economy and society by developing an ethics and integrity framework for research and innovation activities that address environmental and climate challenges.

RE4GREEN KER	Target stakeholder type(s)	Exploitation route
IDENTIFY & MAP environmental & climate ethics issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ All stakeholder types 	Supports uptake of guidelines and recommendations by creating awareness, fostering interest, and promoting engagement in addressing environmental and climate ethics issues.
Operational ("how-to") ethics and integrity GUIDELINES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Researchers ○ Research-performing organisations ○ Industry (incl. SMEs) 	Operational guidelines and procedures encourage the consideration of environmental and climate ethics and integrity issues, across all stages of R&I practice and research areas.
Ethics and integrity RECOMMENDATIONS for policy and risk evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research ethics committee members ○ Research integrity experts ○ Researchers and students ○ Research managers 	Development of new standards for ethics appraisal schemes will influence ethics assessment, impacting R&I behaviour.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Publishers 	Promotes development of new standards for peer review, fostering integration of environmental and climate ethics issues in R&I.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research funders ○ Policymakers 	Recommendations for environmental risk assessment and policy account for environmental and climate ethics issues, including "do no significant harm", and promote new standards for grant allocation, responsible decision-making, and enhancing the societal relevance of products from inception to market entry, all of which influence R&I behaviour.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Citizen scientists ○ Civil society organisations 	Specific citizen science guidelines encourage contribution to co-creation of R&I that incorporates environmental and climate ethics and integrity.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Students ○ Researchers 	New standards of education and training create awareness and promote change in R&I to take

In-person and online TRAINING programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research-performing organisations 	environmental and climate ethics issues into account.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Research ethics committee members ○ Research integrity experts 	Informs research ethics committees and research integrity offices, who can then guide R&I performing actors and help ensure adherence to guidelines.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Citizen scientists ○ Civil society organisations 	Promotes awareness and uptake of guidance in R&I activities.

Table 3 – RE4GREEN KERs and different exploitation routes to target groups

Plan for communication activities

Objectives

RE4GREEN will ensure that all interested individuals and organisations are aware of RE4GREEN's progress, findings, and outputs through targeted communication activities. WP5 will plan and oversee the application of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, including communication activities. Communication activities to promote RE4GREEN will increase the visibility of the project, spread awareness, and reach a wide range of stakeholders. As part of WP5, the consortium will ensure timely and clear communication of the project to all relevant stakeholder groups through a variety of communication channels (Table 4). Each communication channel is accompanied by a list of the stakeholders that the channel targets. This does not mean that stakeholders who are not listed will not be informed by specific channels. However, the main targets of communication will define the language that will be used on those channels. For example, press releases will mainly target laypeople, so the language used will be as simple as possible, while LinkedIn will mainly target our peers, so the language will be more technical yet jargon-free.

Channels of communication

RE4GREEN consortium partners have substantial experience in using communication channels. This asset, combined with a streamlined "communication operationalisation" outlined within this DEC Plan, will lead to effective and efficient communication with all relevant stakeholders. Pre-existing institutional, organisational, and personal social media accounts, along with established networks and expertise across relevant fields within the consortium will serve as a foundation for effectively disseminating the project's results and outputs. The RE4GREEN consortium has completed a plan that specifies the minimum key performance indicators (KPIs) to be achieved via the project's communication channels (Table 4).

Website: The project's website will keep relevant stakeholders and the wider public informed about the progress of the project and provide access to deliverables, publications, events, and outputs.

Online communication: Different types of online communication activities will be undertaken:

- Promotional videos (PVs): The first PV will present a general overview of the project, and the second PV will present the project's main outputs and outcomes. During the kick-off meeting, consortium members listed ideas for the promotional videos (see Annex).
- E-newsletters: The newsletters will be sent to subscribers (who subscribe via a form on the project website). They will include an overview of the project's progress, i.e., deliverables submitted, participation at conferences, new collaborations, available training materials, and policy recommendations (see Annex).
- Webinars: General and targeted webinars for organisations (internally & externally).

Social media: LinkedIn and Twitter will be instrumental in reaching all relevant stakeholders to communicate RE4GREEN's progress. A Social Media Manager will keep the project's social media presence active. Social media will be used to initiate collaboration with relevant projects and stakeholders. During the RE4GREEN kick-off meeting, consortium members listed several projects and profiles to connect with on social media (see Annex).

Scientific conferences: Participation in scientific conferences on research ethics, research integrity, environmental and climate ethics, and environmental and climate R&I. This may include the following:

- [World Conference on Research Integrity](#)
- [ENRIO Congress on Research Integrity Practice](#)
- [EARMA Conference](#)
- [Asia Pacific Research Integrity Conference](#)
- [International Sustainability Transitions Conference](#)
- [4S/EASST](#) (deadline 12/2)
- [ESOF](#)
- Annual Meeting AEM (registered)
- ECSA 2026 (bi-annual Citizen Science Conference)
- Sustainability/Environmental Conferences (SAICEM/CLIMATE COPS/IPBES/ITPGRFA ROME)
- IAEE/ENAI 2026 A'dam
- Mechanical, Physics, Agricultural etc. Conferences
- EUREC (WG2)
- REAL DEAL C50 Forums
- ESDIT/4TU.ETHICS

Scientific publications: Publications in leading peer-reviewed field journals. This may include the following:

- [Technological Forecasting and Social Change](#)
- [Environmental Science and Policy](#)
- [Ethics, Policy & Environment](#)
- [Nature Sustainability](#)
- [Journal of Responsible Innovation](#)
- [Research Ethics Journal](#)
- Ethics, Values and Policies
- [Science, Technology and Human Values](#)
- [Environmental Ethics](#)
- JNT for Ed. Int
- [Accountability in Research](#)
- [Science and Engineering Ethics](#)
- [European Journal of Social Science Research](#)

Third-party events: including participation in relevant EU-funded project events (like iRECS cluster meetings and EUREC working group webinars).

Press releases/media pitches: Aimed at newspapers with national circulation in the consortium's national languages.

Public events: Participation in open lectures in Science Museums, European Researcher's Night events, and popular science communication events (e.g., Pint of Science).

Channels	Tool	Indicator	m12	m24	m36
Website	Newsfeed	number	20 (4)	40	70
	Visits	visits	250 (212)	700	2500
Online communication	Promotional videos	number	1	1	2
	E-newsletters	number	2	5	6
	Webinars	number	0	2	4
Social media	Twitter	followers/tweets	300 (388) /20 (22)	500/20	1000/500
		re-tweets/likes	100 (164) /50 (179)	300/200	500/500
	LinkedIn	followers/ posts	80 (142) /20 (21)	150/40	250/80
Scientific conferences	Oral/poster presentations	participations	2 (2)	4	8
Scientific publications	articles	articles	0	1	5
Third-party events	Participation	Participation	5 (3)	10	15
Press releases/media pitches	Newspapers	articles	1	2	4
	E-Magazines	articles	1 (1)	2	4
Public events	Participation	Booth/presentation	-	1	2

Table 4 – RE4GREEN communication channels and their respective KPIs (current progress is shown in red)

Publications and open science

The consortium is well-versed in open science practices and will implement a strong open science approach which will be developed and monitored through Task 6.2. Open science lies at the heart of RE4GREEN's bottom-up approach through the Social Labs, which will ensure the bottom-up participation of a wide range of stakeholders throughout the project duration, including research ethics and integrity experts, researchers, research managers, relevant policymakers, industry actors, citizen scientists, and civil society organisations.

The consortium intends to give the project's results and deliverables the widest possible reach via the project website, emails, social media, and publications, among other platforms. An appropriate Creative Commons licence CC-BY (requiring attribution) or CC-0 (no rights reserved) licence will be used for the project's outputs to ensure that they are shared with minimal restrictions (unless otherwise agreed upon), aside from attribution

to the authors or creators. Open access will be provided to project publications featured in peer-reviewed journals through publication via the “gold” or “green” route. This decision will be based on the publisher selected, the scope of the article (the types of findings it shares), and the input of the partners who have contributed to the publication. The consortium has allocated a budget to cover the cost of gold open-access publishing. For the green route, the consortium members have agreed that the material will be deposited immediately upon publication and that articles will be open access after the shortest embargo period allowed by the respective publication (publishers with short embargo periods, such as 6 months, will be preferred). Furthermore, partners will favour open review processes for publications, such as with the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform (one of the consortium partners is a Collection Advisor at ORE).

Furthermore, project protocols and outputs will be (pre-)registered on Zenodo by the coordinator (UBO) to enhance transparency and promote ethical research practices. Zenodo will serve as the default repository for the project's results unless the consortium identifies a more suitable repository that better aligns with the material and the institutional norms and requirements of the partners (see also Eghbali & Fisher, 2024).

The connections between the objectives; expected results; and appropriate dissemination, exploitation, and communication measures are outlined below (Table 5).

Specific needs	Expected results	D & E & C Measures
Objl: Need for deeper knowledge about the key dimensions and concepts of climate and environmental ethics that are relevant and challenging for REC members, research integrity experts, researchers and RPOs, industry (including SMEs), research managers, policymakers, research funders, students, graduates, and postdocs in universities, NCPs of consortium member countries, civil society organisations, citizen scientists and the general public, and publishers/editors from a research ethics perspective, both for the research process itself and for the societal application of its results to address global climate and environmental challenges.	Objl: Comprehensive analyses of i) climate and environmental ethics issues in terms of their relevance to R&I; and ii) ethics and integrity issues when developing and using scientific knowledge to address global environmental challenges.	Objl: Manuscript(s) in peer-reviewed journals, sessions in conferences on relevant topics, webinar(s); events for early career scientists in graduate schools and at the Science in the City Festival, European Researchers' Night, and EU Open Science Forum; Poster presentation at 8th World Conference on Research Integrity 2024 in Athens.

<p>Obj2: Need to engage relevant and diverse stakeholders in discussing challenges and responses when integrating climate and environmental ethics and integrity issues in R&I activities generally and when advancing the Green Transition to connect science and society.</p>	<p>Obj2: Establishment of a network of stakeholders, including researchers, research funders, policymakers, publishers, citizens, civil society, research ethics and integrity experts, and industry related to climate and environmental ethics in R&I (both within and beyond the ERA).</p>	<p>Obj2: Social Lab participants host a minimum of 20 briefings to different organisations on climate and environmental ethics in R&I; creation of an online Environment and Climate Ethics Social Lab resource platform at the ENERI and The Embassy websites, including cross-sector participant video testimonials.</p>
<p>Obj3: Need to account for environment and climate ethics, climate justice, the "do no significant harm" principle, and other related issues in operational guidelines and strategies on research ethics and integrity.</p>	<p>Obj3: Operational "how-to" guidelines and actionable recommendations accounting for environmental and climate ethics issues in the work of research ethics committees, environmental risk assessment, and R&I policy.</p>	<p>Obj3: Engagement with policymakers in the development of policy recommendations, wide-ranging dissemination of policy briefs; briefing to the Horizon Policy Support Facility; briefing to the JRC European Competence Framework for Research Careers team; updated REC guidance including the ECOC; NCP briefings and Info Days dissemination.</p>
<p>Obj4: Lack of traditional and online training materials to sensitise researchers, members of ethics review boards, and R&I stakeholders to climate and environmental ethics.</p>	<p>Obj4: Open, accessible, traditional, and online training materials for ERA stakeholders (including researchers at different career levels) and ethics review board members (including Horizon Europe ethics appraisal scheme experts).</p>	<p>Obj4: Conducting training; providing open access training materials on platforms like the Embassy of Good Science, ENERI in cooperation with the iRECS project and NERQ network.</p>

Table 5 – Summary of the key elements of the impact section

Conclusion

This report outlines the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities of the RE4GREEN project, aiming to enhance its impact and ensure the sustainability of project results and outputs. The implementation of this plan will be monitored throughout the project and is founded on the consortium's collective efforts.

Annex

Consortium members' contributions to the DEC activities boards during the kick-off meeting.

Collaboration with other projects	Third-party or consortium network events	Social media platforms	Newsletter ideas	Journals & manuscript topics	Science e-magazines & blogs	Promotional videos or other ideas	Conferences
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •NERQ •irecs •BEYOND •ONE EARTH Guardians (Utokyo) •PREPARED 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •EUREC working group webinars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •EMBASSY OF GOOD SCIENCE •UCT_ BioEconomy •EuCitSci •Bio-economy Research Chair •NRIN •NERQ •ECSA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •deliverables submitted •participation conferences •new collaborations •training materials available •policy briefs •make a plan for more engaging blogs aimed at the public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Nature Sustainability •Journal of Responsible Innovation •Research Ethics Journal •Ethics, Values and Policies •Science, Technology and Human Values •Environmental Ethics •JNT for Ed. Int •Accountability in Research •Science and Engineering Ethics •European Journal of Social Science Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •ECSA Newsletter •Euroscientist •LSE Blog 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Webinar/workshop --> ECSA Working Group on Research Ethics or other relevant WG •Micromodules developed in WP4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •4S/EASST (deadline 12/2) •ESOF •WCRI (registered) •Annual Meeting AEM (registered) •ECSA 2026 (bi-annual Citizen Science Conference) •ENRIO •Sustainability/ Environmental Conferences (SAICEM/CLIMATE COPS/IPBES/ITPGRFA ROME) •IAEE/ENAI 2026 A'dam •Mechanical, Physics, Agricultural etc. Conferences •EUREC (WG2) •REAL DEAL C50 Forums •ESDIT/4TV.ETHICS •Annual Conference, Oct 2024, Uni of Twente

References

ECSA (2015) *10 principles of citizen science*. European Citizen Science Platform: ECSA 10 Principles of Citizen Science. <https://eu-citizen.science/resource/88>

Egbali, A. & Fisher, E. (2024) *Data management plan and open science*. RE4GREEN.

